

A Review on Vitamin D Deficiency Associated Metabolic Diseases

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Vitamin-D or Calciferol, a fat-soluble vitamin, which is also called sunshine vitamin, as it is synthesized in the skin on sun exposure and is very necessary for the absorption of calcium in the gut and to maintain calcium, magnesium and phosphate levels in the body. Vitamin D is also responsible for bone mineralization and to prevent various bone associated diseases like osteoporosis, osteomalacia etc. According to the expert committee of Food and Nutrition Board at the National Academics of Services, engineering and Management, an individual below the concentration of 30nmole/litre is considered to be at greater risk of developing deficiency of Vitamin D. Spending more time indoors, unhealthy food habits, use of sunscreen, less exposure to sunlight, high level of melanin pigments are some of the reasons of developing Vitamin D deficiency. Vitamin D is found to be associated with various metabolic syndromes which include a set of conditions where people are at higher risk of heart attack and stroke. Metabolic syndromes include conditions like increase in the waist circumference, higher level of Fasting High Density Lipopolysaccharides, hypertension, inactiveness, overweight or obesity, higher sugar levels and many more. Studies have suggested that Vitamin D deficiency and insufficiency also leads to subclinical atherosclerosis. The deficiency of Vitamin D also seems to be associated with the vitamin D receptor (VDR) expression in adipose tissue, food intake and exercise levels in obese people. *In vitro* studies on animals including human adipocyte cell lines revealed interference of Vitamin D by inhibiting the adipocytes differentiation hence inhibiting adipogenesis in a mice model as well as in human study. Vitamin D is also found to be directly linked with thermogenesis and fat oxidation rates. Furthermore, Vitamin D levels are also observed to be associated with both systolic and diastolic blood pressure as both gets decreased with administration of Vitamin D in person with existing high blood pressure. The evidence suggests that lower level of vitamin D triggers the development of insulin resistance thus non-insulin dependent diabetic mellitus (NIDDM) by deregulating the insulin sensitivity or β -cell function, or both. This review paper aims to study the association between levels of Vitamin D and various metabolic diseases and to develop strategies for the prevention in order to decrease the risk of development of metabolic diseases.

Keywords - non-insulin dependent diabetic mellitus, insulin sensitivity, osteoporosis, osteomalacia, atherosclerosis.